

LAYING SPEED EFFECT ON THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES THERMAL IN AUTOMATED TAPE LAYING PROCESS

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Keywords: thermoplastic composites, automated tape laying, laying speed, thermal field, simulation

ABSTRACT

Effect of the laying speed on the thermal field and heat flux of the thermoplastic composites by using the automated tape laying process was simulated and estimated based on the simulation results for different laying speeds, which was studied with the self-developed simulation program of ANSYS. The results illustrate the non-uniform of the thermal field increases with the laying speed increasing although it can improve the produce efficiency. The central parts of thermoplastic composite near to the mandrel material show a comparable high temperature and this phenomenon is more apparent for the higher laying speed due to the mandrel heat cannot be efficiently released.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the development of technology and production process, the thermoplastic composites have widely applied in aerospace with the laying method for the high specific strength and the corrosion resistance performances. The produce cost and process feature play an important effect on its used in the fields of strict cost control requirement. In recent years, some thermoplastic composites parts have found in civil engineering and motor fields for the short molding cycle based on the mould pressing. However in the aircraft fields, the automated tape laying process was regarded as a real promising method to obtain the quality-satisfied primary and second-primary load carrying parts. Thermal history in the lay-up process has a great effect on the temperature composites quality and it is necessary to study the temperature distribution of the composites in the process of producing the needed structures [1-3]. It will be useful to study the thermal field in the laying process, which was fulfilled by using simulation method with transient thermal model.

The thermal distribution of the layup process is mostly studied by the test method using the sensors based on the previous studies. However, it has the shortages of the high cost and the inevitable errors in the testing process, which can be avoided using the simulation method and has widely used in the actual research. In recent, the thermoplastic composites are commonly produced with the tow winding and strip laying methods and have been acquired widespread concerns of the relate companies and institutes, which has become one of research hotspot in this field [4-5]. The laying process includes the stages of heating and cooling and finishes in a few seconds, which will play an important role as those processes are studied in a cost-efficiency way.

In this study, the effects of the laying speed on the thermal field and heat flux of the thermoplastic composites in the automated laying process are simulated with the self-developed simulation program of ANSYS and the temperature distributions for different laying speeds are studied with the transient thermal analysis, which was conducted with the ANSYS Parametric Design Language (APDL) and birth-death element method to simulate the heater moving of the lay-up head and the laying effect of the layers added into the needed composite parts.

2 THEORETICAL PRINCIPLE AND MATERIALS

2.1 Theoretical principle

The heat transfer of the thermoplastic composite during the laying process can be regarded as the

one dimensional through the thickness direction, which was abided by the heat transfer equation [6-7]

$$k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} = \rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

Here, k is the thermal conductivity, ρ and C are the density and specific heat capacity, respectively.

$$q = h(T_w - T_f) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{T(y,t) - T_i}{T_\infty - T_i} = \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{y}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{hy}{k} + \frac{h^2 \alpha t}{k^2}\right) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{y}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}} + \frac{h\sqrt{\alpha t}}{k}\right) \quad (3)$$

Here, T_i is the solid surface temperature, and T_∞ is the heat temperature of hot gas; α , κ and h are the thermal diffusivity, heat conductivity, and surface convection heat transfer coefficient of the thermoplastic composite laminates, respectively.

2.2 Automated laying process

The heat and laying processes are conducted in ATL process at the same times, in which the prepreg layers are laid in layer and layer at a certain laying speed, as shown in Fig. 1. The distribution of thermal field and hot-gas temperature present obviously influence on the obtained thermoplastic composites by using the automated tape laying. The simulation technology can be efficiently adopted to study those effects in a low cost, which can be used to avoid the disadvantage of the costly traditional method based on the trials and errors [8-9].

Figure 1: Layup pattern of the thermoplastic composites of the ATL process

In the actual laying process of thermoplastic prepreg, the each layer under the heater resource and the followed layers will has the gradient distribution and variation as the process going on, which will affect the crystallinity and thermal field between the adjacent layers. This process was an unsteady heat transfer feature and should be carefully studied its effects on the final composite parts. In this study, the iterative loop analysis was used to calculate the thermal distribution of the composite parts, which show great impact on the mechanical property of the obtained composite structures.

The simulation processes of solving the thermal field in the automated taped laying can be divided into three steps, which are composed of the pre-process, solution and post-process modules (Fig. 2). The load presents variation with the time during the transient thermal analysis, which was firstly divided into several step loads and defined the corresponding values of load and time, respectively. The laminates contain of six thermoplastic prepreg layers with the single layer thickness of 0.188 mm. The laminate length is 60 mm and the heat temperature sets to 600 °C in the simulation. Moreover, the simulated laying speed are respectively set as 5 mm/s, 10 mm/s, 15 mm/s, and 20 mm/s based on the actual manufacture process.

Figure 2: Flow chart of the transient thermal analysis in present study

2.3 Simulation processes

The detailed information of the simulation model and the required input parameters adopted in the simulation are given in Table 1. The iterative flow processes in the simulation process are shown in Fig. 3. During the laying process, the composite material itself and the load distribution change over time, the layer increase and heat moving should be considered in the simulation [10-11].

Figure 3: Detailed flow process diagram of the transient thermal field analysis used in this study

Classification	Detailed items	Value
Geometry models information	Single layer prepreg thickness [mm]	0.188
	Laminate length [mm]	50
	Layer number of the laminates [mm]	6

	Mandrel thickness [mm]	8
	Axial thermal conductivity K_x [W/m°C]	6.5
Thermal properties of the studied laminates	Transverse thermal conductivity K_y [W/m°C]	0.65
	Density (ρ) [kg/m ³]	1562
	Heat capacity c [J/kg°C]	1425
	thermal conductivity k [W/m°C]	237
Thermal properties of the mandrel material	Density (ρ) [kg/m ³]	2700
	Heat capacity c [J/kg°C]	905
Boundary conditions	Convective heat-transfer coefficient of the mandrel under the natural condition h [W/m ² °C]	13
	Convective heat-transfer coefficient of the laminates under the heat gas condition h [W/m ² °C]	25
	Environmental temperature T_∞ (°C)	20
	Initial temperature T_0 (°C)	20

Table 1: Parameters and the boundary conditions of the simulation models

The thermal distribution in the layup processes are studied on the transient analysis with the death-birth element method. The temperature distributions of the thermal field were affected by the laying speed [12]. The laid prepreg layer's temperature will be also affected by the heat gas temperature used in laying the "new" layer due to the heat transfer effect. Physical properties of the thermoplastic composites prepreg under the different temperature are shown in Table 2.

T/°C	K/(W/m·K)		C/(W/m·K)
	K(x)/	K(y)	
0	6	0.6	800
60	6.5	0.65	908
120	7	0.7	1016
180	7.5	0.75	1124
240	8	0.8	1232
300	8.5	0.85	1340
360	9	0.9	2080
390	9.25	0.95	1660
420	9.5	0.9	1663
480	10	0.9	1664

Table2 Thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity properties of the thermoplastic composites

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The laying speed presents a greatly effect on the thermal field on the results of the 20 mm/s, 15 mm/s, 10 mm/s, and 5 mm/s, respectively. The temperature and heat flux distributions of the studied model of 5 mm/s are shown in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b). The counterpart simulation results of the model for the laying speed of 10 mm/s are shown in Figs. 4(c) and 4(d), respectively.

Figure 4: Thermal field (left) and heat flux (right) for different laying speeds: (a) and (b) are the 5 mm/s; (c) and (d) are the 10 mm/s

Figure 5: Thermal field (left) and heat flux (right) for different laying speeds: (a) and (b) are the 15 mm/s; (c) and (d) are the 20 mm/s

The thermal field and heat flux distributions of the studied model for the laying speed of 15 mm/s are shown in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b). The counterpart results of the model for the 20 mm/s are shown as the Figs. 5(c) and 5(d), respectively. The following aspects can be concluded based on the simulation results, which are composed of: (1) the temperature gradient of the mandrel of 10 mm/s present a larger value compared with that of 5 mm/s for the higher thermal conductivity of the mandrel and it has more time for the heat under the comparable smaller laying speed; (2) the temperature distribution

difference of the mandrel decreases as the laying speed increases; specially the temperature gradient of the mandrel at 15 mm/s have a larger value compared with that of 20 mm/s for the mandrel heat cannot be efficiently released and then cause a high temperature distribution. Results of the heat flux distribution from simulation also show the similar features for the four different kinds of laying speed. The uneven of the thermal field distribution increases as the increasing of the laying speed and the suitable speed need be decided to balance the produce cost and the final properties of the obtained composite structures. The uneven degree of the thermal field distribution increases as the increasing of the laying speed and the suitable speed need be determined to comprehensive trade off the produce cost and the mechanical properties of the obtained composite structures.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Effects of the laying speed on the thermal distribution of the thermoplastic composites in the automated tape laying process were studied using the simulation method and estimated in this study. Four kinds of the laying speed of 5, 10, 15, and 20 mm/s were used to analysis its effects on the thermal field and heat flux features. The results show the laying speed plays an important effect on the thermal field of the composites and a small laying speed is good to obtain a uniform thermal field. The gradient of the temperature increases as the increasing of laying speed, but it can effectively decreases the cost of the obtained composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the Beijing Municipal Science and Technology Project, Grant No. Z151100002815021.

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